

Progress Report

CRYPL

Unpuzzling the role of cryptic plasmids in bacterial evolution

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Report of Task 1

Distinction between Cryptic and Non-Cryptic Plasmids

The objective of Task 1 was to classify plasmids as cryptic or non-cryptic based on the presence of genes associated with antibiotic resistance, virulence, or heavy metal resistance. To this end, all complete bacterial plasmids available in the PlasmidScope (<https://plasmid.deepomics.org/>) database were retrieved, resulting in a dataset of 208354 plasmid sequences. In addition, a collection of 2058 plasmids generated within the OH-DART (<https://research-information.bris.ac.uk/en/publications/one-health-drivers-of-antibacterial-resistance-quantifying-the-re>) and SPaRK (<https://researchportal.bath.ac.uk/en/projects/spark-the-rates-and-routes-of-transmission-of-multidrug-resistant-2>) projects was included in the analysis.

Plasmid sequences were screened using ABRicate (<https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>) against the ResFinder, VFDB and BacMet2 databases to identify antibiotic resistance genes, virulence factors and heavy metal resistance determinants, respectively. Among the complete plasmids retrieved from PlasmidScope, 28151 carried antibiotic resistance genes, 8198 carried virulence-associated genes, and 45277 carried heavy metal resistance genes.

Overall, 56133 plasmids encoded at least one of these traits and were therefore classified as non-cryptic, whereas 152221 plasmids lacked all three categories of genes and were classified as cryptic. Notably, 2429 non-cryptic plasmids simultaneously encoded antibiotic resistance, virulence, and heavy-metal resistance determinants.

In the subset of 2058 plasmids obtained from the OH-DART and SPaRK projects, no antibiotic resistance or virulence genes were identified. BacMet2 screening detected heavy metal resistance determinants in 501 plasmids. Accordingly, these plasmids were classified as non-cryptic, while the remaining 1557 plasmids were classified as cryptic. The completion of this task resulted in curated datasets of cryptic and non-cryptic plasmids that will serve as the basis for the mobility and functional analyses planned in Tasks 2 and 3.

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